

PRODUCT CREDENTIALS AFFECTING CONSUMER CHOICES ON HEALTH GOODS AND SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

Adults and senior citizens in the market are playing vital roles in the market wherein their choices and decisions on buying health goods and services are affected by the product credentials triggered by the demand for reliable products during a health crisis. Thus, this research project investigates the preferred choices of 52 health consumers of health goods and services in terms of their product credentials. In-depth market survey as research instrument was administered to the study to extract responses on how the consumers both adult and senior citizen choose health goods and services based on their preferred product credentials in term of; recommended by reputable organization, credential manufacture of production, price range, effectiveness/testimony of the society, product the is less risky, celebrity endorsement, good service, benefits of the product. The research findings showed that the product credentials have affected consumer's choices and decisions on health goods and services. The respondents highly prioritized the products that are beneficial to their health, recommended by the reputable organizations and manufacture's credentials, moderately prioritized the products that have less risks, good services, and society's testimony, poorly prioritized the product's price and products which endorsed by celebrities. Both adults and senior citizens are prioritizing products which the manufacture's credential is proven and effectiveness of the products is tested. This study is important to map out the effects of product credentials affecting the consumer's choices and decisions. Furthermore, these credentials are important consideration for manufacturers and producers of health goods and services.

Keywords: Product credentials, adults and senior citizens, consumer's choices, reputable organizations, Philippines